

Appendix B.1 - Systematic Literature Review Protocol

Screening Round	Starting number of papers	Inclusion and Exclusion criteria	Total excluded
Round 1	2059	Exclusions: Reason 1: Abstracts do not feature SOBM concept as core topic Reason 2: Supply chain focus or CSR focus instead of business model focus	1008
Round 2	1051	Exclusions: Reason 1: Inaccessible papers Reason 2: Additional duplicates Reason 3: Non-journal content Reason 4: Non-SOBM focus revealed from introduction section Reason 5: Retractions Reason 6: Paper lacks theoretical, conceptual or review contribution	626
Round 3	425	Exclusions: ungeneralizable contribution due to sector or macro-level focus.	255
Round 4	170	Exclusions: Papers do not define SOBM concepts used.	32

Result: 138 included papers (*see other Appendix document*)

Appendix B.2 - Set of Articles Considered for Review

Title	Authors	Year	Journal
Business Models for Sustainability From a System Dynamics Perspective	Abdelkafi and Tauscher	2016	Organization & Environment
Does the combination of sustainable business model patterns lead to truly sustainable business models? Critical analysis of existing frameworks and extensions	Abdelkafi et al	2023	Journal of Business Economics
Review and Categorisation of Support Types for Business Model Innovation for Sustainability	Ademi and Klungseth	2024	Management Review
Business management perspectives on the circular economy: Present state and future directions	Ahmad et al	2023	Technological Forecasting & Social Change
Circular Economy Business Models: The Complementarities with Sharing Economy and Eco-Innovations Investments	Aldieri et al	2021	Sustainability
The sustainability performances of sustainable business models	Alonso-Martinez et al.	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Sustainable business models for social enterprises in developing countries: a conceptual framework	Armstrong and Grobbelaar	2023	Management Review Quarterly
Stakeholder engagement in business models for sustainability: The stakeholder value flow model for sustainable development	Attanasio et al	2021	Business Strategy and the Environment
Addressing the design-implementation gap of sustainable business models by prototyping: A tool for planning and executing small-scale pilots	Baldassarre et al	2020	Journal of Cleaner Production
Circular economy as a driver to sustainable businesses	Barros et al	2021	Cleaner Environmental Systems
Sustainable business models: Researchers as design thinkers for problem-driven research	Bastian and Caputo	2024	Strategic Change
Sustainable Business Model in the Product-Service System: Analysis of Global Research and Associated EU Legislation	Battles-delaFuente et al	2021	Environmental Research and Public Health
Design principles for sustainability assessments in the business model innovation process	Bhatnagar et al	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production
Investigating Circular Business Model Innovation through Keywords Analysis	Bigliardi and Filippelli	2021	Sustainability
An eco-critical perspective on business models: the value triangle as an approach to closing the sustainability gap	Biloslavo et al	2017	Journal of Cleaner Production

Sustainable business models and organizational boundaries—A literature review	Bjartmarz and Bocken	2024	Business Strategy and the Environment
Digital Platforms for the Circular Economy: Exploring MetaOrganizational Orchestration Mechanisms	Blackburn et al	2023	Organization & Environment
Mapping the emergence of a new organisational form: An exploration of the intellectual structure of the B Corp research	Blasi and Sedita	2021	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management
Circular business model innovation in consumerfacing corporations	Bocken and Konietzko	2022	Technological Forecasting & Social Change
Classification of Sustainable Business Models: a Literature Review and a Map of Their Impact on the Sustainable Development Goals	Boffa and Maffei	2021	FME Transactions
Business models for sustainable innovation: state-of-the-art and steps towards a research agenda	Boons and Ludeke-Freund	2013	Journal of Cleaner Production
Circular entrepreneurial ecosystems: a Quintuple Helix Model approach	Borrero and Yousafzai	2024	Management Decision
Digital sustainable business models: Using digital technology to integrate ecological sustainability into the core of business models	Bottcher et al	2023	Information Systems Journal
A FRAMEWORK TO EXPLORE THE FUNCTIONING AND SUSTAINABILITY OF BUSINESS MODELS	Bradley et al	2020	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Exploring How Usage-Focused Business Models Enable Circular Economy through Digital Technologies	Bressanelli et al	2018	Sustainability
A tool for collaborative circular proposition design	Brown et al	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Consumption in the Circular Economy: A Literature Review	Camacho-otero et al	2018	Sustainability
Sustainable international business model innovations for a globalizing circular economy: a review and synthesis, integrative framework, and opportunities for future research	Chabowski et al	2023	Journal of International Business Studies
Linking circular economy and digitalisation technologies: A systematic literature review of past achievements and future promises	Chauhan and Parida	2022	Technological Forecasting & Social Change
Integrating circular business models and development tools in the circular economy transition process: A firm-level framework	Chen et al	2020	Business Strategy and the Environment
Which innovations for Circular Business Models? A product life-cycle categorisation	Chioatto et al	2024	Industry and Innovation

The economic viability of the sharing economy business model and its environmental impact	Chomachaei et al	2024	European Journal of Operational Research
Investigating the key success factors within business models that facilitate long-term value creation for sustainability-focused start-ups	Christodoulou et al	2024	Business Ethics, the Environment & Responsibility
Incumbents and business model innovation for the sharing economy: Implications for sustainability	Ciulli and Kolk	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production
Sustainable business model innovation and scaling through collaboration	Ciulli et al	2022	Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions
Sustainable by design: An organizational design tool for sustainable business model innovation	Coffay and Bocken	2023	Journal of Cleaner Production
Dynamic business modeling for sustainability: Exploring a system dynamics perspective to develop sustainable business models	Cosenz et al	2019	Business Strategy and the Environment
Business model patterns in the sharing economy	Curtis	2021	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Towards sustainability? Forest-based circular bioeconomy business models in Finnish SMEs	D'Amato et al	2020	Forest Policy and Economics
Regenerative business strategies: A database and typology to inspire business experimentation towards sustainability	Das and Bocken	2024	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Circular Economy Business Models: a Repertoire of Theoretical Relationships and a Research Agenda	De Angelis	2022	Circular Economy and Sustainability
Open strategy and dynamic capabilities: A framework for circular economy business models research	De Angelis et al	2023	Business Strategy and the Environment
Untangling business model outcomes, impacts and value	Dembek et al	2022	Business Strategy and the Environment
Embracing the variety of sustainable business models: A prolific field of research and a future research agenda	Dentchev et al	2018	Journal of Cleaner Production
Linking Sustainable Business Models to Socio-Ecological Resilience Through Cross-Sector Partnerships: A Complex Adaptive Systems View	Dentoni et al	2020	Business & Society
The Competitiveness of Firms through the Sustainable Business Model: A Decade of Research	Di Tullio et al	2018	L'industria
The Circular Economy: Recent debates and research trends	Džajić Uršič et al	2024	Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Evelopment

Business Model Innovation for Sustainability: Towards a Unified Perspective for Creation of Sustainable Business Models	Evans et al	2017	Business Strategy and the Environment
A systemic logic for circular business models	Fehrer and Wieland	2021	Journal of Business Research
Circular economy business models: The state of research and avenues ahead	Ferasso et al	2020	Business Strategy and the Environment
Business model innovation for sustainability: a new framework	Ferlito and Faraci	2021	Innovation & Management Review
Start-ups and entrepreneurial ecosystems in the circular economy: A multi-level approach for safe and just planetary boundaries	Ferreira et al	2024	International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship
Business Models For Industrial Symbiosis: A Taxonomy Focused on the Form of Governance	Fraccascia et al	2019	Resources, Conservation and Recycling
A Stakeholder Theory Perspective on Business Models: Value Creation for Sustainability	Freudenreich et al	2020	Journal of Business Ethics
Circular Bioeconomy Business Models to Overcome the Valley of Death. A Systematic Statistical Analysis of Studies and Projects in Emerging Bio-Based Technologies and Trends Linked to the SME Instrument Support	Gatto and Re	2021	Sustainability
The circular economy and circular economic concepts a literature analysis and redefinition	Geisendorf and Pietrulla	2018	Thunderbird International Business Review
Drivers and barriers for circular business model innovation	Geissdoerfer et al	2022	Business Strategy and the Environment
The Circular Economy and Sustainability: A Systematic Literature Review	Gil-Lamata and Latorre-Martinez	2022	Management Letters
Sustainable business model: A review and framework development	Goni et al	2021	Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy
Digital sustainable entrepreneurship: A business model perspective on embedding digital technologies for social and environmental value creation	Gregori and Holzmann	2020	Journal of Cleaner Production
Digital sustainable business model innovation: applying dynamic capabilities approach (DSBMI-DC)	Hajihedari et al	2023	Foresight
How do circular start-ups achieve scale?	Han et al	2023	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Business research for sustainable development: How does sustainable business model research reflect doughnut economics?	Hausdorf and Timm	2022	Business Strategy and the Environment

Bottom-up dynamics in circular innovation systems	Henry et al	2024	Journal of Industrial Ecology
The Business Model in Sustainability Transitions: A Conceptualization	Hernandez-Chea et al	2021	Sustainability
Drivers and barriers of circular economy business models: Where we are now, and where we are heading	Hina et al	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production
Circular business models: Business approach as driver or obstructor of sustainability transitions?	Hofmann	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production
Social business as a sustainable business model: making capitalism anti-fragile	Hysa et al	2018	Sustainability Science
Exploring the impact of sustainable value proposition on firm performance	Ilyas and Osiyevskyy	2022	European Management Journal
Newly developed green technology innovations in business: paving the way toward sustainability	Islam	2023	Green technology innovations in business
Scalability of Sustainable Business Models in Hybrid Organizations	Jablonski	2016	Sustainability
HOW COMPANIES INNOVATE BUSINESS MODELS AND SUPPLY CHAINS FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY: A MULTIPLECASE STUDY AND FRAMEWORK	Kaipainen et al	2022	International Journal of Innovation Management
TOWARDS CRYSTALLIZING CIRCULAR BUSINESS MODELS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE	Karman	2020	Journal of Sustainability Science and Management
A systematic review of sustainable business models: Opportunities, challenges, and future research directions	Karuppiah et al	2023	Decision Analytics Journal
Interconnected or Disconnected? A Review of Sustainability, Resilience, and Sustainable Business Model Constructs in the Academic Business Literature	Kassier	2023	Journal of the Knowledge Economy
Pushing Forward the Transition to a Circular Economy by Adopting an Actor Engagement Lens	Katrien Verleye, Arne De Keyser, Néomie Raassens, Alex A. Alblas, Fernando C. Lit, Josephina C. C. M. Huijben	2023	Journal of Service Research
Industry 4.0 and sustainable development: A systematic mapping of triple bottom line, Circular Economy and Sustainable Business Models perspectives	Khan et al	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Towards regenerative business models: A necessary shift?	Konietzko et al	2023	Sustainable Production and Consumption

A Systematic Literature Review on the Transition to Circular Business Models for Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)	Kuik et al	2023	Sustainability
Circular economy and sustainable development: a review and research agenda	Lamba et al	2024	Circular economy and sustainable development
The Role of Consumers in Business Model Innovations for a Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy	Lang et al	2023	Sustainability
The potential of sharing economy business models for sustainable value creation	Laukkanen and Tura	2020	Journal of Cleaner Production
The Circular Business Framework for Building, Developing and Steering Businesses in the Circular Economy	Lauten-Weiss and Ramesohl	2021	Sustainability
Influencing factors driving collaboration in circular business models	Leder et al	2023	International Journal of Logistics
Influential Factors for Value Creation within the Circular Economy: Framework For Waste Valorisation	Leder et al	2020	Resources, Conservation and Recycling
Sustainable Business Model Based on Digital Twin Platform Network: The Inspiration from Haier's Case Study in China	Li et al	2020	Sustainability
Sustainable business models: Providing a more holistic perspective	Lozano	2018	Business Strategy and the Environment
Sustainable entrepreneurship, innovation, and business models: Integrative framework and propositions for future research	Ludeke-freund	2020	Business Strategy and the Environment
The sustainable business model pattern taxonomy – 45 patterns to support sustainability-oriented business model innovation	Ludeke-freund et al	2018	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Value uncaptured perspective for sustainable business model innovation	M. Yang, S. Evans, D. Vladimirova, P. Rana	2017	Journal of Cleaner Production
Artificial intelligence capabilities for circular business models: Research synthesis and future agenda	Madanaguli et al	2024	Technological Forecasting & Social Change
Design Options for Sustainable and Open Business Models: A Taxonomy-Based Analysis	Mais and Bauernhansl	2024	Sustainability
Dynamic sustainable business modelling: exploring the dynamics of business model components considering the product development framework	Maresova et al	2022	Applied Economics

How Hybrid Organizations Adopt Circular Economy Models to Foster Sustainable Development	Maria Cristina Zaccone, Cristina Santhià, and Martina Bosone	2022	Sustainability
Circular business model innovation and cognitive framing: Addressing the “missing micro”	Matoh et al	2024	business
Sustainable business models as boundary-spanning systems of value transfers	Meike Brehmer	2018	Journal of Cleaner Production
What is unique about sustainable business models for the base of the pyramid?	Mendez-Leon et al	2024	Business Strategy and the Environment
Towards Systematic Sustainable Business Model Innovation: What Can We Learn from Business Model Innovation	Minatogawa et al	2022	Sustainability
Transforming sustainability challenges into competitive advantage: Multiple case studies kaleidoscope converging into sustainable business models	Morioka et al	2017	Journal of Cleaner Production
Green and sustainable business models: historical roots, growth trajectory, conceptual architecture and an agenda for future research—A bibliometric review of green and sustainable business models	Najmaei and Sadeghinejad	2023	Scientometrics
Defining Value in Sustainable Business Models	Neesham et al	2023	Business & Society
In the eye of the beholder: Stakeholder perceived value in sustainable business models	Norris, S.	2024	Studies in Business and Economics
Circular Business Models: Defining a Concept and Framing an Emerging Research Field	Nußholz	2017	Sustainability
Collaborative Sustainable Business Models: Understanding Organizations Partnering for Community Sustainability	Ordinez-Porce et al	2021	Business & Society
Valuing Value in Innovation Ecosystems: How Cross-Sector Actors Overcome Tensions in Collaborative Sustainable Business Model Development	Oskam et al	2021	Business & Society
Digital-sustainable business models: Definition, systematic literature review, integrative framework and research agenda from a strategic management perspective	Palmie et al	2024	International Journal of Management Reviews

Circular products and business models and environmental impact reductions: Current knowledge and knowledge gaps	Patricia van Loon, Derek Diener, Steve Harris	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
A research model for circular business models–Antecedents, moderators, and outcomes	Pietrulla and Frankenberger	2022	Sustainable Futures
Exploring business models for sustainability: A bibliographic investigation of the literature and future research directions	Preghenella and Battistella	2021	Business Strategy and the Environment
The Role of Linked Legitimacy in Sustainable Business Model Development	Press et al	2020	Industrial Marketing Management
Value creation and appropriation in economic, social, and environmental domains: Recognizing and resolving the institutionalized asymmetries	Ritala et al	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Business Model Innovation to Create and Capture Resource Value in Future Circular Material Chains	Roos	2014	Resources
Customer-perceived value in the circular economy: A multidimensional framework	Sairanen et al.	2024	Industrial Marketing Management
Low-carbon business models: Review and typology	Sairanen et al.	2024	Industrial Marketing Management
Circular economy strategies on business modelling: Identifying the greatest influences	Salvador et al	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Framing and assessing the emergent field of business model innovation for the circular economy: A combined literature review and multiple case study approach	Santa-Maria et al	2021	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Business model innovation for sustainability: An investigation of consumers' willingness to adopt product-service systems	Sattari et al	2020	Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science
Business Models for Sustainability: A Co-Evolutionary Analysis of Sustainable Entrepreneurship, Innovation, and Transformation	Schaltegger et al	2016	Organization & Environment
Business Models for Sustainability: Choices and Consequences	Schneider and ClauB	2020	Organization & Environment
Circular economy and innovation: A look from the perspective of organizational capabilities	Sehnm et al	2022	Business Strategy and the Environment
User-centered circular value propositions – approaches in practice and research	Selvefors et al.	2024	Resources, Conservation and Recycling
Anatomy of sustainable business model innovation	Shakeel et al	2020	Journal of Cleaner Production

Missing Attention to Power Dynamics in Collaborative Multi-Actor Business Models for Sustainability	Skritsovali et al	2023	Sustainability
Green Business Models: definitions, types, and life cycle analysis	Solesvik et al	2022	Forum Scientiae Oeconomia
Aligning servitization and circularity: The role of institutional confluence in sustainable business models	Stabler et al.	2024	Journal of Cleaner Production
Business models for sustainability and firms' external relationships—A systematic literature review with propositions and research agenda	Stal et al	2023	Business Strategy and the Environment
Conceptualizing a “Sustainability Business Model”	Stubbs and Cocklin	2008	Organization & Environment
A transitions framework for circular business models	Susur and Engwall	2023	Journal of Industrial Ecology
Certified B corporations: An approach to tensions of sustainable-driven hybrid business models in an emerging economy	Tabares	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Exploring the role of dynamic capabilities in digital circular business model innovation: Results from a grounded systematic inductive analysis of 7 case studies	Thomas van Eeouchd, Andrea Ganzaroli	2023	Journal of Cleaner Production
BUSINESS MODELS FOR SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY: AN EXPERT STUDY	Tunn et al	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production
Value Creation in Circular Business Models: The Case of a US Small Medium Enterprise in the Building Sector.	Unal et al	2019	Conservation and Recycling
An Ontology for Strongly Sustainable Business Models: Defining an Enterprise Framework Compatible With Natural and Social Science	Upward, Antony, Jones Peter	2015	Organization & Environment
Corporate-entrepreneur collaborations to advance a circular economy	Veleva, Vesela, Bodkin, Gavin	2018	Journal of Cleaner Production
Pushing Forward the Transition to a Circular Economy by Adopting an Actor Engagement Lens	Verleye et al.	2024	Journal of Service Research
Three circular business models that extend product value and their contribution to resource efficiency	Whalen, Katherine	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production
Towards a more Circular Economy: Proposing a framework linking sustainable public procurement and sustainable business models	Witjes, Sjors, Lozano, Rodrigo	2016	Resources, Conservation and Recycling
Eco-innovation and Circular Business Models as drivers for a circular economy	Xavier Vence, Ángeles Pereira	2019	Contaduría y Administración

Beyond Sustainability, Toward Resilience, and Regeneration: An Integrative Framework for Archetypes of Regenerative Innovation	Yadav, V., Yadav, N.	2024	Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management
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